

Influence of Intensity on the Velocity of Photochemical Reactions.

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In publications (Bhattacharya and Dhar, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, **169**, 381; 1928, **175**, 357; Mukerji and Dhar, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1926, **32**, 501; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, **32**, 1308) from these laboratories we have investigated the influence of the variation of intensity of the incident radiation on the velocity of several photochemical reactions. By changing the diameter of the aperture of an Iris diaphragm, the amount of light falling on the reaction vessel and hence the intensity was varied. In all the reactions the velocities in the dark were deducted from the total change observed in light in order to get the velocity in light alone. The changes in the concentrations of the reacting substances were determined either by suitable titrations or spectrophotometric measurements. The diameters of the aperture of the Iris diaphragm used were 2 cm., 0·8 cm. and 0·4 cm. in most of the reactions. The intensity of light was taken to be directly proportional to the area of the aperture through which the light passed before falling on the reaction vessel.

The source of light in most reactions was a 1,000 watt gas-filled tungsten-filament lamp operated at 4·6 amperes. In some reactions sunlight was also utilized, whilst in others light-filters were used. The reactions investigated in these laboratories may be roughly classified in the three following groups:—

(1) Velocity tends to be proportional to the square of the incident radiation.

(2) Velocity is almost directly proportional to the intensity.

(3) Velocity becomes nearly proportional to the square-root of the intensity of the incident radiation.

From our investigations with more than forty photochemical reactions we infer that the velocities of the majority of the reactions investigated in these laboratories are proportional to the square-root of the incident radiation. Hence we have come to the conclusion that the velocities of really photochemical reactions are proportional to the square-root of the intensity of the incident radiation

We have advanced the view that the two important factors,

which are of consequence in the relation between intensity and the velocity of a reaction, are--

- (a) The amount of absorption of the incident radiation by the reacting system.
- (b) The acceleration of the reaction in presence of light.

When the absorption of radiation is high and the reaction is not markedly photochemical in nature and the velocity of the reaction in the dark is appreciable, direct proportionality or even square of intensity is likely to be observed. On the other hand, when the reaction is highly photochemical in nature and the velocity of the dark reaction is practically negligible, square-root relationship will be expected.

It will be evident, therefore, from the foregoing lines that if a reaction, which is proportional to the square of the intensity of the incident radiation, can be greatly accelerated by the incidence of strong light, it should show a tendency to follow the direct or square-root relationship. On the other hand, reaction following the square-root relationship can be made to be proportional directly to the intensity, if the dark velocity of such a reaction can be greatly accelerated and the reacting system is exposed to radiation which is not intense and slightly absorbed by the reacting system.

We have been successful in changing the relationship between the intensity and velocity by changing the velocity of the dark reaction and the intensity and quality of the incident radiation in the following reactions :—

1. Potassium oxalate and iodine.
2. Rochelle salt and bromine.
3. Quinine sulphate and chromic acid.
4. Sodium formate and iodine.

Dhar (*Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch. Amsterdam*, 1916, **18**, 1084) was the first to investigate the kinetics of the reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine in the light and in the dark, and he found that the velocity of the reaction is greatly accelerated by light, and it is greater in sunlight than in diffused light. Later on Berthoud and Bellenot (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, **7**, 307) investigated the same reaction and found it to be proportional to the square-root of the incident radiation, and this conclusion has been supported by Briers, Chapman, and Walters (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **129**, 562). Recently Mukerji and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, **32**, 1308) observed that the reactions between potassium oxalate and iodine and ammonium

oxalate and iodine is proportional to the square-root of the incident radiation in presence of white light obtained from a 1,000 watt gas-filled tungsten-filament lamp and also radiation of wave-length 4725 Å.

We have reinvestigated the reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine in radiations of wave-length 5650Å and 7304Å using different intensities. The previous workers dissolved their iodine in potassium iodide which is a marked retarder in the reaction. Hence in order to accelerate the dark reaction, we have avoided potassium iodide and have only used an aqueous solution of iodine. The following experimental results have been obtained.

N-Potassium oxalate and N/550-iodine (aqueous), 10 c.c. each.
Temperature = 20°.

Wave-length.	Diameter of the aperture.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ Semimolecular.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ After deducting the dark reaction. $k_{\frac{1}{2}}(dark) = 0.00353.$
5650 ⁰ Å	2 cm.	0.00968	0.00615 (I)
	0.8	0.00502	0.00149 (II)
	0.4	0.00400	0.00047 (III)
7304 ⁰ Å	2 cm.	0.00816	0.00463 (I)
	0.8	0.00456	0.00103 (II)
	0.4	0.00382	0.00029 (III)

Wave-length.	Ratio of velocities.	If directly proportional to change in intensity.	If proportional to the square-root of the change in intensity.
5650 ⁰ Å	$\frac{I}{II} = 4.1$	$\frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25$	$\sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$
	$\frac{II}{III} = 3.2$	$\frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4$	$\sqrt{4} = 2$
	$\frac{I}{III} = 13$	$\frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25$	$\sqrt{25} = 5$
7304 ⁰ Å	$\frac{I}{II} = 4.5$	$\frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25$	$\sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$
	$\frac{II}{III} = 3.6$	$\frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4$	$\sqrt{4} = 2$
	$\frac{I}{III} = 16$	$\frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25$	$\sqrt{25} = 5$

The foregoing results show that the reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine (dissolved in potassium iodide), which is proportional to the square-root of the intensity of radiation (from a 1,000 watt gas-filled tungsten-filament lamp and of light of wave-length 4725 Å), tends to be directly proportional to the intensity of radiation of wave-length 5650 Å and 7304 Å in absence of potassium iodide. We have observed that these radiations are only slightly absorbed by the reacting system.

Mukerji and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) have shown that the velocity of reaction between Rochelle salt and bromine in presence of sodium acetate under the influence of radiation of $\lambda=4725$ Å is practically proportional to the square of the intensity of incident radiation. Hydrogen ions markedly retard the velocity of the reaction and in order to accelerate the dark reaction we have used sodium acetate and borax.

N/13.93-Rochelle salt (5 c.c.) and N/180-bromine (10 c.c.) in presence of N/6.7-sodium acetate (5 c.c.).

Temperature = 20°.

Wave-length.	Diameter of the aperture.	k_1 Monomolecular.	k_1 After deducting the dark reaction.
			k_1 (dark) = 0.001.
1000 Watt lamp.	2 cm.	0.00907	0.00807 (I)
	0.8	0.00449	0.00349 (II)
	0.4	0.00275	0.00175 (III)
5650 Å (a)	2 cm.	0.00446	0.00346 (I)
	0.8	0.00160	0.00060 (II)
	0.4	0.00115	0.00015 (III)
			<i>In presence of N/625-borax.</i>
			k_1 (dark) = 0.001.
5650 Å (b)	2 cm.	0.00461	0.00361 (I)
	0.8	0.00167	0.00067 (II)
	0.4	0.00118	0.00018 (III)

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In presence of N/250-borax.

Wave-length.	Diameter of the aperture.	k_1 Monomolecular.	k_1 After deducting the dark reaction.
5650 Å (c)	2 cm.	0.00608	0.00436 (I)
	0.8	0.00223	0.00051 (II)
	0.4	0.00182	0.00010 (III)

k_1 (dark) = 0.00172.

In presence of N/105-borax

Wave-length.	Diameter of the aperture.	k_1	k_1 After deducting the dark reaction.
5650 Å (d)	2 cm.	0.00750	0.00550 (I)
	0.8	0.00262	0.00062 (II)
	0.4	0.00210	0.00010 (III)

k_1 (dark) = 0.0020.

Wave-length.	Ratio of velocities.	If directly proportional to change in intensity.	If proportional to the square-root of the change in intensity.
1000 Watt lamp.	$\frac{I}{II} = 2.3$	$\frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25$	$\sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$
	$\frac{II}{III} = 2$	$\frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4$	$\sqrt{4} = 2$
	$\frac{I}{III} = 4.6$	$\frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25$	$\sqrt{25} = 5$
5650 Å (a)	$\frac{I}{II} = 5.7$	$\frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25$	$\sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$
	$\frac{II}{III} = 4$	$\frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4$	$\sqrt{4} = 2$
	$\frac{I}{III} = 23$	$\frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25$	$\sqrt{25} = 5$
5650 Å (b)	$\frac{I}{II} = 5.4$	$\frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25$	$\sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$
	$\frac{II}{III} = 3.7$	$\frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4$	$\sqrt{4} = 2$
	$\frac{I}{III} = 20$	$\frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25$	$\sqrt{25} = 5$

Wave-length.	Ratio of velocities.	If directly proportional to change in intensity.	If proportional to the square-root of the change in intensity.
5650 Å (e)	$\frac{I}{II} = 8.5$	$\frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25$	$\sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$
	$\frac{II}{III} = 5.1$	$\frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4$	$\sqrt{4} = 2$
	$\frac{I}{III} = 43.6$	$\frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25$	$\sqrt{25} = 5$
5650 Å (d)	$\frac{I}{II} = 9$	$\frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25$	$\sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$
	$\frac{II}{III} = 6.2$	$\frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4$	$\sqrt{4} = 2$
	$\frac{I}{III} = 55$	$\frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25$	$\sqrt{25} = 5$

Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **111**, 707) investigated the kinetics of the reaction between quinine sulphate and chromic acid in the dark and found that the reaction is greatly accelerated by light Mukerji and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) investigated the influence of variation of intensity on this reaction in presence of sulphuric acid using the total light from a 1,000 watt gas filled tungsten-filament lamp. They observed that the reaction is proportional to the square of the incident radiation. We have re-investigated the reaction using different amounts of sulphuric acid.

M/75-Quinine sulphate in N/11.7-sulphuric acid and M/88.8-chromic acid, 10 c.c. each.

Temperature = 20°. Source = 1,000 watt lamp.

Diameter of the aperture.	k_1 Monomolecular.	k_1 After deducting the dark reaction.	
		k_1 (dark) = 0.00004.	
A. 2 cm.	0.00147	0.00143	(I)
0.8	0.000857	0.000817	(II)
0.4	0.000145	0.000105	(III)

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M/75-Quinine sulphate in N/2·3-sulphuric acid and M/88·8-chromic acid.

Diameter of the aperture.	k_1	k_1
	Monomolecular.	After deducting the dark reaction.
		k_1 (dark) = 0·000196
B. 2 cm.	0·00463	0·00443 (I)
0·8	0·000973	0·000677 (II)
0·4	0·000346	0·000150 (III)

M/75-Quinine sulphate in 7N-sulphuric acid and M/88·8-chromic acid.

Diameter of the aperture.	k_1	k_1
	Monomolecular.	After deducting the dark reaction.
		k_1 (dark) = 0·00346.
C. 2 cm.	0·00628	0·00593 (I)
0·8	0·000959	0·000613 (II)
0·4	0·000457	0·000111 (III)

Ratio of velocities.	If directly proportional to change in intensity.	If proportional to the square root of the change in intensity.
A. $\frac{I}{II} = 4·5$	$\frac{3·14}{0·5024} = 6·25$	$\sqrt{6·25} = 2·5$
$\frac{II}{III} = 3$	$\frac{0·5024}{0·1256} = 4$	$\sqrt{4} = 2$
$\frac{I}{III} = 13·6$	$\frac{3·14}{0·1256} = 25$	$\sqrt{25} = 5$
B. $\frac{I}{II} = 6·5$	$\frac{3·14}{0·5024} = 6·25$	$\sqrt{6·25} = 2·5$
$\frac{II}{III} = 4·5$	$\frac{0·5024}{0·1256} = 4$	$\sqrt{4} = 2$
$\frac{I}{III} = 29·5$	$\frac{3·14}{0·1256} = 25$	$\sqrt{25} = 5$
C. $\frac{I}{II} = 9·7$	$\frac{3·14}{0·5024} = 6·25$	$\sqrt{6·25} = 2·5$
$\frac{II}{III} = 5·6$	$\frac{0·5024}{0·1256} = 4$	$\sqrt{4} = 2$
$\frac{I}{III} = 53·5$	$\frac{3·14}{0·1256} = 25$	$\sqrt{25} = 5.$

The reaction between sodium formate and iodine in presence of radiation of wave-length, $4725 \overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$ has been found by Mukerji and

Dhar to be proportional to the square of the intensity of incident radiation. In order to accelerate the dark reaction a very small amount of potassium iodide was used in dissolving iodine. Both sodium acetate and borax were used as buffer solutions.

N/6.25-Sodium formate (5 c.c.) + N/204-iodine⁻ (10 c.c.) dissolved in very little KI and N/6.7-sodium acetate (5 c.c.).

Temperature = 20°. Source = 1000 watt lamp.

Diameter of the aperture.	k_1 Monomolecular.	k_1 After deducting the dark reaction.	
		k_1 (dark)	k_1 (dark)
A. 2 cm.	0.0259	0.0190	(I)
0.8	0.0102	0.0033	(II)
0.4	0.00785	0.00088	(III)

N/6.25-Sodium formate (5 c.c.) + N/204-iodine in little KI (10 c.c.) and N/250-borax.

k_1 (dark) = 0.00691.

B. 2 cm.	0.0182	0.0113	(I)
0.8	0.0081	0.0012	(II)
0.4	0.00714	0.00023	(III)

N/6.25-Sodium formate (5 c.c.) + N/204-iodine (10 c.c.) in 10% KI + N/250-borax (5 c.c.).

k_1 (dark) = 0.00015.

C. 2 cm.	0.00572	0.00422	(I)
0.8	0.00290	0.00140	(II)
0.4	0.00210	0.00060	(III)

Ratio of velocities.	If directly proportional to change in intensity.	If proportional to the square root of the change in intensity.
A. $\frac{I}{II} = 5.8$	$\frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.5$	$\sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$
$\frac{II}{III} = 3.8$	$\frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4$	$\sqrt{4} = 2$
$\frac{I}{III} = 21.6$	$\frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25$	$\sqrt{25} = 5$

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Ratio of velocities.	If directly proportional to change in intensity.	If proportional to the square root of the change in intensity.
B. $\frac{I}{II} = 9.4$	$\frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25$	$\sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$
$\frac{II}{III} = 5.2$	$\frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4$	$\sqrt{4} = 2$
$\frac{I}{III} = 4.9$	$\frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25$	$\sqrt{25} = 5$
C. $\frac{I}{II} = 3$	$\frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25$	$\sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$
$\frac{II}{III} = 2.3$	$\frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4$	$\sqrt{4} = 2$
$\frac{I}{III} = 7.03$	$\frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25$	$\sqrt{25} = 5$

In order to make sure that the absorption of radiation is proportional to the intensity of the incident radiation, we have determined the absorption of the incident radiation by a radio-micrometer. We have observed that the amount of radiation absorbed is directly proportional to the intensity of the incident radiation.

The foregoing experimental results show that by increasing the velocity of the dark reaction and exposing it to radiation which is slightly absorbed by the reacting system, a truly photochemical reaction, which is proportional to the square-root of the incident radiation or the amount of energy absorbed, becomes directly proportional to the intensity of the incident radiation or the amount of energy absorbed.

On the other hand, a photochemical reaction which is proportional to the square of the incident radiation or is directly proportional, can be made to be proportional to the square-root of the incident radiation by decreasing the dark reaction velocity and increasing the photochemical velocity.

Our experimental results and conclusions throw a flood of light on the highly controversial question of the relation between intensity and velocity in the reaction between chlorine and hydrogen. Draper (*Phil. Mag.*, 1843, 23, 401), Mrs. Chapman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1521), Kornfeld and Muller (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, 117, 242) observed that the photochemical reaction between chlorine and hydrogen is directly proportional to the intensity of the incident

radiation ; whilst Baly and Barker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 653) showed that the velocity increases more rapidly than the intensity.

All these workers have used total light from electric bulbs. Recently Marshall (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1453) has investigated the same problem in presence of mercury arc light.

Marshall's results show that the combination of chlorine and hydrogen in presence of mercury lamp radiation, which is more intense than the light used by previous workers, is proportional to less than the square-root of the incident radiation.

Draper, Baly and Barker and Mrs. Chapman used electrolytic gas which always contains small amounts of oxygen. Kornfeld and Müller removed oxygen from the hydrogen, but the chlorine they used may have contained a little oxygen. On considering the details of the experiments of Mrs. Chapman, and those of Baly and Barker, we are of the opinion that there was more oxygen present in Baly and Barker's experiments than in Mrs. Chapman's gas and this will be evident from the following lines from Baly and Barker's paper:—"During the course of this work we encountered considerable difficulty owing to the production of oxygen in the reaction vessel."

Moreover the light intensity in the experiment of Mrs. Chapman was greater than in the case of Baly and Barker. It is well known that oxygen markedly retards the photochemical combination of hydrogen and chlorine ; hence, it appears that the photochemical reaction velocity in the experiments of Baly and Barker was not as much accelerated as that of Mrs. Chapman. We have already emphasised that greater the acceleration of the reaction by the absorption of incident light, the less is the chance of observing a direct or a square relationship between intensity and velocity. Consequently Baly and Barker observed a ten-fold increase in intensity by increasing the light six-fold, whilst Mrs. Chapman working with a purer reacting system, containing less oxygen and under more intense light than that used by Baly and Barker observed about 5.5-fold increase of velocity on six-fold increase of light intensity. The results of Kornfeld and Muller are on the same line as those obtained by Mrs. Chapman.

Marshall working with very pure reacting substances and with intense light from a mercury arc obtained a relation, which is less than square-root for the same chemical change. Hence the photochemical combination of chlorine and hydrogen can show less than

square-root, direct or nearly square relationship depending on the acceleration caused by light. These results are exactly of the same type as those obtained by us with bromine and Rochelle salt, sodium formate and iodine, quinine sulphate and chromic acid and potassium oxalate and iodine.

Direct proportionality between intensity and velocity has been found in the cases of hydrolysis of chloroplatinic acids (Boll, *Ann. Phys.*, 1914, *ix*, 2, 5, 226), the decompositions of solutions of hydrogen peroxide (Tian, *ibid*, 1916, *ix*, 5, 248), potassium cobalt-oxalate (Vránek, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1917, 23, 336) and potassium mangani-oxalate (Ghosh and Kappanna, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 127), and for the initial photolysis of uranyl formate solutions (Hatt, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1918, 92, 513). Now in all these cases there is an appreciable dark reaction and in presence of light the velocity of the reaction is not enormously increased. Moreover Mukerji and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) found that a solution of dicyanin can be decolourised by passing oxygen in the dark and the effect of light intensity on the photochemical bleaching of dicyanin shows direct proportionality. On the other hand Warburg and Negelein (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1923, 106, 191) have shown that in the carbon dioxide assimilation reaction sensitised by chlorophyll, the rate of assimilation increases less rapidly than the intensity. It is well known that no combination of carbon dioxide and moisture takes place in the dark even in presence of chlorophyll and hence carbon assimilation is a typically photochemical reaction where the velocity does not increase proportionately with the intensity of light. According to Berthoud (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1925, 21, 554; also Berthoud and Nicolet, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1927, 10, 475) square root relationship holds for addition of bromine to cinnamic acid, to α -phenylcinnamionitrile and to stilbene and the oxidation of hydriodic acid in presence of iodine. In all these cases the reactions are highly accelerated by light and the reaction velocity in the dark is very small in comparison with the photochemical velocity.

Bodenstein and Lutkemeyer (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 114, 208) have announced that the union of hydrogen and bromine in light is proportional to the square-root of the energy absorbed when the intensity of light is kept constant. It will be interesting to observe that the velocity of the same reaction taking place in the light is 80 times greater than that taking place in the dark. Consequently the combination of bromine and hydrogen is highly photochemical

in nature. Briers and Chapman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 133, 1807) have recently found that the rate of interaction of hydrogen and bromine for very high intensity of light approximates to values which are square-root to the values of the intensity but for low intensities, the rate becomes more nearly equal to values proportional to intensity. Those reactions where square-root relationship is observed are largely accelerated by light and their thermal reactions are extremely slow in comparison with the reaction in light alone. In these reactions many molecules are readily activated by the absorption of radiation on illumination and consequently further increase in light intensity is not likely to increase the velocity of reaction markedly.

In previous papers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 707; *Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch. Amsterdam*, 1920, 23, 308; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 948; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 141, 1; *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1925, 31, 283) the conception of activation of molecules in explaining the mechanism of thermal and photochemical reactions has been emphasised. It has been postulated that chemical reactions take place between activated molecules. It has also been pointed out that the effects of increase of temperature, of light and of chemical catalysts in a reaction are intimately connected and are possibly identical in nature. It has also been shown that those reactions which are very sensitive to the influence of temperature are also very sensitive to the influence of light. Moreover, we have proved (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 707; 1923, 123, 1856; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, 121, 1561; 1924, 134, 172; 1928, 169, 381; 1920, 176, 372) with numerous reactions that light acting as a positive catalyst markedly lower the temperature coefficient of a reaction; for, in presence of light the transformation from an inactive to active molecules would have already taken place and therefore, temperature should have less additional accelerating effect. Consequently those reactions which are highly photochemical in nature have much less chance of showing direct proportionality between the incident light and velocity of reaction.

A fast dark reaction when illuminated, has much less chance of showing direct proportionality relationship than a slow reaction, because in a fast reaction many more molecules are in the active state and there is less chance of further activation of molecules on increased illumination than in the case of slow reactions. As a matter of fact, our experimental results show that the reaction

between potassium permanganate and lactic acid, or tartaric acid or citric acid in presence of strong light increases much less rapidly than intensity and these reactions have been proved to be fast in the dark.

The majority of researchers in photochemistry have assumed that the amount of a chemical change in a given system, effected by light of a specified wave-length, is directly proportional to the light absorbed. Following the lead of Draper this has been called the first law of photochemistry. Although this is a fundamental principle of greatest importance, the experimental evidence of its universal validity is not conclusive. From a survey of our experimental results obtained with more than forty photochemical reactions and the existing literature in photochemistry, we come to the conclusion that the amount of chemical change of a truly photochemical system where the reaction is largely accelerated by light, is proportional to the square root or even less than square-root of the light absorbed.

In recent years Berthoud (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, 7, 324) has emphasised that the primary process in the photochemical reactions with halogens as one of the reacting substances is the dissociation of halogen molecules into atoms as the result of their absorption of light, the halogen atoms then reacting at a rate proportional to the first power of their concentration. This contention of Berthoud appears to be supported by the fact that several photochemical reactions are proportional to the square-root of the incident radiation.

In foregoing papers (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 1308; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 169, 281; 1928, 175, 257) we have shown that this point of view of Berthoud need not always be correct. We have observed that the reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine is proportional to the square-root of the incident radiation from a 1000 watt gas-filled tungsten filament lamp; whilst the reaction between sodium lactate and iodine is directly proportional to the intensity. If we assume that in presence of light a molecule of iodine is atomised, we can explain the intensity effect on the reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine, but this conception that the halogen molecules are atomised on illumination does not help us in understanding the mechanism of those photochemical reactions with halogen as one of the reacting substances and where the velocity of reaction is directly proportional or proportional to the square of the intensity of the incident radiation.

Our experimental results show that the reaction between sodium lactate and iodine is only slightly accelerated by light and consequently the inactive molecules available for activation on illumination is large and hence direct proportionality is observed. Moreover we have shown in this paper that in the case of several photochemical reactions, the relation between velocity and intensity of incident radiation changes from $\frac{1}{2}$ to 2. In other words, we have shown definitely that the ratio of the velocity and intensity of one and the same photochemical reaction can vary from a proper fraction to 2 or more depending on the acceleration of the photochemical reaction over the thermal reaction. We are of the opinion that this explanation of the difference of intensity effect on different photochemical reactions is more satisfactory than any of the existing views

Baly and Barker and others have assumed that those reactions, which do not obey Einstein law of photochemical equivalence, should deviate from Draper's law. We have shown that the bleaching of neocyanin in air follows Einstein's law of photochemical equivalence but this reaction is proportional to the square-root of the incident radiation. Moreover, the reactions between iodine and a tartrate or lactate or citrate or ferrous sulphate and in several other cases the velocities are directly proportional to the intensity of incident radiation and hence follow Draper's law, although they deviate considerably from Einstein's law of photochemical equivalence ; in all these reactions many more molecules react per quantum of light absorbed.

Hence we are of the opinion that those reactions which obey Einstein's law need not follow Draper's law and *vice versa*.

Summary.

(1) The influence of the change of intensity on the velocity of a photochemical reaction has been investigated with 35 photochemical reactions in solution in these laboratories.

(2) The reaction between potassium oxalate and aqueous iodine tends to be directly proportional to the intensity of radiation of wave-lengths 5650 Å and 7304 Å. The same reaction in presence of potassium iodide when exposed to white light or light of wave-length 4725 Å is proportional to the square-root of the incident radiation.

(3) The reaction between sodium potassium tartrate and bromine appears to be proportional to the square-root of the incident radiation

from a 1000 watt lamp. In presence of radiation of wave-length 5650 Å, it is directly proportional to the incident radiation and in presence of borax it tends to be proportional to the square of the incident radiation.

(4) The reaction between quinine sulphate and chromic acid appears to be proportional to the square-root or direct or more than direct of the incident radiation as the concentration of sulphuric acid is increased.

(5) The reaction between sodium formate and iodine dissolved in small amount of potassium iodide and sodium acetate tends to be proportional to the incident radiation. In presence of borax the velocity of the same reaction becomes about nine-fold when the intensity is increased six times. In presence of excess of potassium iodide and borax it tends to be proportional to the square-root of the incident radiation.

(6) The photochemical reaction between hydrogen and chlorine becomes proportional to the square-root of the incident radiation in presence of strong light and directly proportional when the acceleration is not high. An explanation of the existing divergent data on the influence of radiation on this reaction has been advanced.

(7) The combination of bromine and hydrogen becomes proportional to the square root in strong light and directly proportional in light of low intensity.

(8) The two important factors which are of consequence in the relation between intensity and velocity of a photochemical reaction are (a) the amount of absorption of the incident radiation by the reacting system and (b) the acceleration of the reaction in presence of light.

(9) Truly photochemical reactions should tend to be proportional to the square-root or less than square-root of the incident radiation.

(10) Those photochemical reactions which obey Einstein's law of photochemical equivalence need not follow Draper's law and *vice versa*.

